

SUPPORTING ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD WITH EDUCATIONAL DIGITAL GAMES

Uğur Enis Kılıç, Ceren Gürkan, Aybüke Uyanık, Sibel Sönmez

Ege University Faculty of Education, İzmir-Türkiye

Early childhood is a critical period in which the foundations of an individual’s cognitive, emotional and social skills are laid. The competencies gained during this period can directly affect children’s academic and professional success in later years (Heckman , 2006). Entrepreneurial skills in particular are among the basic competencies that need to be supported during this period, and they contribute to children’s development of skills such as creativity, problem solving, risk taking, independent thinking and collaboration (Gibb , 2002; Amabile, 1996). Supporting entrepreneurship education from an early age is of great importance in the process of adapting to changing world conditions and raising innovative individuals (Fayolle & Gailly , 2008).

At this point, educational digital games stand out as an effective tool for supporting entrepreneurship education. Digital games encourage children to learn through trial and error by providing them with opportunities to explore and experience and develop their creativity (Prensky , 2001). In addition, game-based learning environments allow children to strengthen their problem-solving skills, make independent decisions and assess risks (Granic , Lobel & Engels, 2014). This process helps children develop entrepreneurial thinking skills in both individual and team-based activities and encourages them to produce solutions for real-world problems (Gee , 2003).

Acquiring entrepreneurial skills at an early age not only enables individuals to be innovative and productive in the future, but also contributes to social development. The impact of entrepreneurship education will increase when educators and parents adopt game-based strategies that encourage children's curiosity and desire to explore, and make learning fun and interactive (Malone & Lepper , 1987). In this context, the integration of educational digital games into the education process offers an important opportunity to reveal children's entrepreneurial potential and raise them as more equipped individuals. Thus, supporting entrepreneurship education in early childhood will provide long-term contributions to the economic and social development of society as well as the career development of the individual (Neck & Greene , 2011).

Literature Review on Supporting Entrepreneurial Skills in Early Childhood with Educational Digital Games

Early childhood is a critical period for children to acquire the skills they need to live independently. Entrepreneurial skills are among the 21st century skills that new generations need and should be acquired at an early age (Aral & Kılıçoğlu, 2022).

Entrepreneurship is a process of restructuring oneself through discovery. This process begins in the early years of life and continues with lifelong learning (UIL, 2020). Acquiring entrepreneurial skills in early childhood supports coping with difficulties and achieving set goals in later years of life.

Entrepreneurial skills acquired at an early age help children make independent career plans and look at the situations they encounter from a broad perspective (Gartner, 1988; Demolins, 2015).

Entrepreneurial Skills

1. Creativity and Innovation

Entrepreneurship is closely related to the ability to generate new ideas and find different solutions to existing problems (Stevenson et al., 1985).

2. Risk-Taking and Decision Making

Entrepreneurs are generally individuals who can deal with unknown situations and manage uncertainties (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000).

3. Problem-Solving Skills

Problem solving is one of the key components of entrepreneurship (Rodrigues et al., 2012).

4. Self-Confidence and Independence

Entrepreneurs are generally self-confident and independent individuals (Christianti et al., 2015).

5. Leadership and Collaboration

Successful entrepreneurs are individuals who can communicate and collaborate effectively with people (Marques et al., 2013).

6. Critical Thinking and Opportunity Recognition

Entrepreneurs identify opportunities based on uncertain and incomplete data and develop new solutions by analyzing opportunities (Venkataraman, 1997).

7. Resilience and Adaptability

Entrepreneurs are generally individuals who do not give up in the face of failure, but rather move forward by learning from it (Aslam, 2021).

8. Financial Literacy and Resource Management

Entrepreneurial skills include financial literacy and effective use of resources (Demirdöğen, 2020).

Entrepreneurship in early childhood includes studies on developing entrepreneurship from an early age. Entrepreneurship studies for children are carried out in the form of activities, digital applications and workshops (Aral & Kılıçoğlu, 2022). Educational digital games, one of the entrepreneurship studies, are designed to provide individuals with certain knowledge and skills (Bétrancourt, 2005). In 1982, “Snooper Troops” was released to support problem-solving skills; and in 1985, “Where in the World is Carmen Sandiego” was released to develop geography knowledge. Studies conducted in the

following years have shown that digital games support problem-solving skills (Göldağ, 2020; Efe Kendüzler, 2023).

In his research, Aslam (2021) examined teachers' expectations for developing entrepreneurial skills in early childhood and defined the connection between play and entrepreneurial skills in early childhood education. The findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between play and entrepreneurial skills, and that entrepreneurial skills develop through games in early childhood. Teachers and parents who participated in the research agreed that entrepreneurial skills develop from an early age.

When other studies investigating the entrepreneurial skills of digital games in early childhood are examined; although specific studies examining the direct effect of digital games on entrepreneurial skills are limited, it is seen that educational digital games support children's entrepreneurial skills such as problem solving, creativity and critical thinking (Ocak, 2013; Efe Kendüzler, 2023). Studies examining the effect of digital games on entrepreneurial skills in early childhood are limited in the literature. This research aims to present new perspectives and contribute to the field with a detailed examination of the subject.

Literature Review on Supporting Entrepreneurial Skills in Early Childhood with Educational Digital Games

In the literature review, it has been determined that entrepreneurship skills in early childhood have a multidimensional structure including creativity, innovation, risk taking, decision making, problem solving skills, self-confidence, independence, leadership, cooperation, critical thinking, recognition of opportunities, resilience, flexibility, financial awareness, and resource management (Aslam, 2021; Christianti et al., 2015; Demirdöğen, 2020; Marques et al., 2013; Rodrigues et al., 2012; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Stevenson et al., 1985; Venkataraman, 1997). In this context; The keywords "Creativity, Innovation, Risk-Taking, Decision Making, Problem-Solving Skills, Self-Confidence, Independence, Leadership, Collaboration, Critical Thinking, Opportunity Recognition, Resilience, Adaptability, Financial Literacy, Resource Management" were determined.

To reach educational games, the keywords "Educational game" OR "educational digital game" OR "educational digital games" OR "educational video game" OR "educational video games" OR "digital game-based learning" OR "DGBL" OR "Games Based Learning" OR "Educational Computer Games" OR "Game-based learning" OR "Game-Based" OR "Digital Game-Based" were determined.

Finally, to identify individuals in early childhood, the keywords "preschool" OR "preschoolers" OR "kindergarten" OR "young children" OR "young childrens" OR "young students" OR "pre-school" were determined. As a result of the screening, 96 studies were reached and it was determined that there was sufficient research richness for systematic compilation.

In order to determine whether there are systematic reviews examining the role of educational digital games on entrepreneurial skills of individuals in early childhood, searches were conducted on the 'Web of Science'. The searches were also conducted by adding the keywords "entrepreneurship" or "entrepreneurial", which define entrepreneurial skills in general. As a result of the search, no systematic review was found that directly addresses entrepreneurial skills of individuals in early childhood in a holistic manner.

Results of Literature Review Related to Educational Games Recommended by Common Sense Media Organization

Founded in 2003, the non-profit organization “Common Sense Media” aims to provide guidance to families and educational institutions by rating age-appropriate media content (Common Sense Media, nda). The full names of 37 games that the organization determined to be suitable for early childhood were converted into keywords and searched in the “Web of Science” database (Common Sense Media, ndb). As a result of the search, two studies were found examining the effect of the educational game “Khan Academy Kids” on children’s early literacy skills (Arnold et al., 2021) and the effect of the game “RelationShapes” on children’s spatial skills (Polinsky et al., 2021). This shows that there is a limited number of studies on games recommended directly to families and schools by “Common Sense Media” and that there is a significant gap in the literature in this area. Therefore, the literature search related to specific games did not yield any results.

REFERENCES

1. Aral, N., & Kılıçoğlu, EA (2022). *Entrepreneurship in early childhood . International European Journal of Managerial Research* , 6(11), 15-27.
2. Göldağ, B. (2020). Digital games: Positive and negative effects. *Journal of Eurasian Social and Economic Research* , 7(2), 170-181.
3. Aslam, R. (2021). Entrepreneurship Skills Among Young Learner Through Play Strategy: a Qualitative Study. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 9(2), 64-74.
4. UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning. (2020). *Embracing a culture of lifelong learning: Contribution to the Futures of Education initiative* . UNESCO.
5. Gartner, W. B. (1988). “Who is the entrepreneur?” is the wrong question. *Journal American Small Business*, 12(4), 11-32.
6. Demolins, E. (2015). *Anglo Saksonların üstünlük sebepleri nelerdir? Çeviri Editörü: Bahri Ata, Pegem Akademi Yayıncılık, Ankara*
7. Stevenson, H. H., Roberts, M. J. & Grousbeck, H. I. (1985). *New Business Ventures and the Entrepreneur*. Irwin, Homewood, IL.
8. Shane, S., & Venkataraman, S. (2000). The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(1), 217-226.
9. Santos-Rodrigues, H., Faria, J., Cranfield, D., & Morais, C. (2010). The influence of intellectual capital on entrepreneurial orientation: A study on Brazilian and Portuguese firms. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 9(1), 58-73.
10. Christianti, M., Yuniarsih, T., & Ahman, E. (2015). The influence of self-confidence and independence on entrepreneurial intentions among university students. *International Journal of Management and Administrative Sciences*, 3(4), 1-15.
11. Marques, C. S., Ferreira, J. J., Gomes, D. N., & Rodrigues, R. G. (2013). Entrepreneurship education: How psychological, educational and sociological variables are related to entrepreneurial intention. *Education + Training*, 54(8/9), 657-672.
12. Venkataraman, S. (1997). The distinctive domain of entrepreneurship research. *Advances in Entrepreneurship, Firm Emergence and Growth*, 3, 119-138.
13. Aslam, T. (2021). Entrepreneurial resilience: Learning from failure and persisting in the face of adversity. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Research*, 10(2), 45-67.

14. Rebetez , C., & Bétrancourt, M. (2005). video game research in cognitive and educational sciences . *Cognition , Brain, Behavior* , 9(3), 423-446.
15. Demirdöğen, Y. (2020). Analysis of the Islamic fintech ecosystem in Europe. *Süleyman Demirel University Journal of Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 25 (4), 469-481.
16. Efe Kendüzler, S. (2023). The effects of educational games, games in mathematics centers and digital games on children's mathematics and self-regulated learning skills.
17. Ocak, M. (2013). Educational digital games: theory, design and application.
18. Common Sense Media. (nda). *Our mission* . Access date: [4.02.2025], <https://www.commonsensemedia.org/about-us/our-mission>
19. Common Sense Education. (ndb). *Educational games for preschool and kindergarten* . Access date: [4.02.2025]____<https://www.commonsense.org/education/lists/educational-games-for-preschool-and-kindergarten>
20. Arnold, D. H., Chary, M., Gair, S. L., Helm, A. F., Herman, R., Kang, S., & Lokhandwala, S. (2021). A randomized controlled trial of an educational app to improve preschoolers’ emergent literacy skills. *Journal of Children and Media*, 15(4), 457-475.
21. Polinsky, N., Flynn, R., Wartella, E. A., & Uttal, D. H. (2021). The role of spatial abilities in young children’s spatially-focused touchscreen game play. *Cognitive Development*, 57, 100970.
22. Amabile, T. M. (1996). *Creativity in context: Update to the social psychology of creativity*. Westview Press.
23. Fayolle, A., & Gailly, B. (2008). From craft to science: Teaching models and learning processes in entrepreneurship education. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 32(7), 569–593. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090590810899838>
24. Gibb, A. A. (2002). In pursuit of a new “enterprise” and “entrepreneurship” paradigm for learning: Creative destruction, new values, new ways of doing things and new combinations of knowledge. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 4(3), 233–269. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2370.00086>
25. Gee, J. P. (2003). What video games have to teach us about learning and literacy. *Computers in Entertainment*, 1(1), 20–20. <https://doi.org/10.1145/950566.950595>
26. Granic, I., Lobel, A., & Engels, R. C. M. E. (2014). The benefits of playing video games. *American Psychologist*, 69(1), 66–78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0034857>
27. Heckman, J. J. (2006). Skill formation and the economics of investing in disadvantaged children. *Science*, 312(5782), 1900–1902. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1128898>
28. Malone, T. W., & Lepper, M. R. (1987). Making learning fun: A taxonomy of intrinsic motivations for learning. In R. E. Snow & M. J. Farr (Eds.), *Aptitude, learning, and instruction: Volume 3. Conative and affective process analyses* (pp. 223–253). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
29. Neck, H. M., & Greene, P. G. (2011). Entrepreneurship education: Known worlds and new frontiers. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 49(1), 55–70. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-627X.2010.00314.x>
30. Prensky, M. (2001). *Digital game-based learning*. McGraw-Hill.